

Educating Ethical Judgement in a Pluriverse – Pluriversal Ethical Reflection as a Framework for Formation

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Abstract

This article addresses a core concern in contemporary philosophy and theology of education: how education can cultivate moral judgement and ethical responsibility in contexts marked by epistemological pluriversality. Decolonising perspectives reveal that dominant educational paradigms often continue to rely on universalist assumptions. Instrumental and competence-based approaches tend to marginalise issues of normativity, meaning and moral formation. This raises foundational questions about educational purpose, ethical orientation and responsibility in plural educational contexts.

The article presents the ‘Pluriversal Ethical Reflection Framework’ as a conceptual and reflective framework, rather than as a methodology or intervention. The framework draws on Dooyeweerd’s philosophy of the fifteen modal aspects, recent Dooyeweerdian scholarship, decolonial thought on epistemic justice (Moncrieffe), virtue ethics and meaning-oriented reflection. Together, these sources form an integrative architecture. It interrelates three educational levels: macro-level normativity (Dooyeweerd), meso-level contextual interpretation (‘Political, Economic, Social-cultural, Technological, Environmental and Legal’ analysis as a normative layer), and micro-level ethical self-development (Meaning-Oriented Reflection). The architecture acts within a *Bildung*-oriented pedagogical horizon. Two educational cases illustrate how the framework supports ethical judgement in higher education and intercultural leadership education.

Conceptually, the article contributes to theology and philosophy of education by articulating educational normativity as hopeful, relational and practice-oriented. Normativity is understood as disclosed within lived educational reality, rather than imposed through procedural control or abstract prescription.

Keywords

Bildung; decolonising; educational design; ethics; ethics education; normativity; philosophy of education; pluriversality; reflection; theology of education; virtues; worldviews

Introduction

Contemporary education unfolds within conditions of accelerating epistemological plurality and moral complexity. Globalisation, post-colonial critique, migration and digitalisation have reshaped educational contexts in thoughtful manners. These confront educators and learners with opposing worldviews, ethical imaginaries and meaning-systems. Classrooms, curricula

and institutions increasingly function as sites of encounter between co-existing epistemic traditions. This in contrast to spaces governed by a single, shared frame of reference. Plurality can enrich educational experience. At the same time, it unsettles inherited assumptions regarding shared norms, universal values and the purposes of education itself.

In response to this complexity, educational systems have turned toward competence-based and outcome-oriented frameworks. These promise transparency, comparability and governability by translating learning into observable skills, measurable outcomes and key performance indicators. From a managerial perspective, these offer clarity and control. Yet critics within philosophy and theology of education argue that such responses risk marginalising education's formative and normative dimensions. When education becomes primarily procedural, questions of meaning, ethical responsibility and human flourishing tend to decline (Horkheimer and Adorno 2007, 3–9).

These developments pose a fundamental challenge for contemporary philosophy of education. This accounts for ethical formation and educational normativity under conditions of epistemological plurality.

Parallel to this proceduralising of education, decolonial and pluriverse perspectives have gained increasing importance. These approaches challenge the presumed neutrality of dominant educational paradigms. They expose how Western epistemology has historically functioned as a universalising framework that marginalised alternative ways of knowing and being (Mignolo 2018, ix–xv). Education, from this perspective, cannot be understood as purely technical or instrumental. It is implicated in broader struggles over knowledge, power and ethical orientation.

This situation raises a central pedagogical question: How can education remain normatively oriented, while honestly accepting epistemological plurality? Sustaining pluralism without ethical orientation risks relativism or procedural neutrality. This confirms that universal norms risk reproducing epistemic domination. Addressing this tension constitutes a core task for philosophy of education. This, as it concerns the educational meaning of normativity, moral judgement and formation in plural educational contexts.

The article contributes to that task by presenting the 'Pluriversal Ethical Reflection Framework' (PERF) as a conceptual framework for ethical formation in educational contexts. The framework integrates three analytical levels: macro, meso and micro. These connect through a pluriverse horizon and are steadied by virtue ethics. Rather than offering a method, intervention or assessment instrument, the PERF functions as a reflective architecture. It supports meaning-oriented reflection, ethical responsibility and formation in the tradition of *Bildung*.

Pluriversality and the Educational Condition

Pluriversality, therefore, does not suspend normativity but rather places it under reflective pressure. Education is called to cultivate judgement in a precise manner, because learners live within multiple worlds of meaning.

The notion of the *pluriverse* foregrounds the coexistence of multiple, historically situated worlds of meaning rather than a single epistemic centre. Pluriversality challenges the modern

epistemological aspiration to universality. It does so by recognising that knowledge, values and ethical orientations are embedded in cultural, linguistic, historical and political contexts (Mignolo 2018, ix–xv; Maldonado-Torres 2007, 242–5). Knowledge is not just gathered or transferred. It is lived, and normatively structured within specific lifeworlds.

Marlon Moncrieffe deepens this insight by emphasising that education is always shaped by a locus of enunciation. This is the socio-historical position from which knowledge is produced and approved. Dominant curricula appear to present themselves as universal or neutral. This while marginalising alternative epistemologies and lived experiences. They thereby reproduce forms of cognitive injustice (Moncrieffe 2022, 1–8). Consequently, decolonising education cannot be reduced to representational inclusion. It requires questioning of the epistemic assumptions that define acceptability, accuracy and authority within education.

Within educational contexts, this critique problematises long-standing assumptions about neutral curricula and objective knowledge transmission. As Ngũgĩ wa Thiong’o demonstrated decades earlier, education has frequently served as a mechanism of epistemic domination by privileging languages, narratives and forms of rationality, while silencing others (Ngũgĩ wa Thiong’o 1986, 3–12). Moncrieffe extends this critique by showing how assessment methods, academic discussion and pedagogical norms continue to privilege Western epistemologies. Doing this while under the guise of inclusion and diversity (Moncrieffe 2022, 9–12).

Yet pluriversality also introduces pedagogical vulnerability. When plurality is affirmed without reflective mediation, education risks collapsing into epistemic simultaneity. Being a form of “flat pluralism” in which perspectives are present but are not meaningfully connected. Such pluralism may promote tolerance, yet it rarely seems to support ethical formation. Moncrieffe warns that decolonial education requires ethical orientation, not epistemic indifference (Moncrieffe 2025). Plurality confronts and unsettles. However, it itself does not educate.

From the standpoint of philosophy of education, the challenge is therefore not whether plurality exists. The challenge is how education can respond to plurality in a way that cultivates judgement, responsibility and ethical judgement. This challenge is not unique to current debate. Earlier educational thinkers already faced similar tensions. Comenius’ pansophic vision sought to honour epistemic diversity while maintaining a unifying commitment to wisdom and human betterment (Comenius 1657/2019, I–II). His insistence on integration rather than fragmentation anticipates current attempts to think pluriversality without normative lessness (Woldring 2016, 87–102).

Normativity, Bildung and Moral Formation in Education

Normativity in education refers to questions of what ought to be valued, cultivated and pursued in education. Despite persistent attempts to modify education as a neutral, functional or skills-oriented, normativity remains manifest. A pedagogical decision implicitly conveys assumptions about what constitutes a worthwhile life, responsible action and appropriate social participation.

The tradition of *Bildung* offers a sustained philosophical response to this condition. *Bildung* understands education as a process of educators guiding learners' self-development. It is oriented toward ethical maturity and human flourishing, rather than simple adaptation to economic or institutional demands (Taylor 2017, 421–6). Learning is not confined to cognitive acquisition. It engages affective, self-directed and ethical dimensions of the person.

Within this horizon, ethical formation in educational practice is not an add-on to learning outcomes. It is integral to education's purpose. *Bildung* presupposes that learners are capable of self-reflective assumptions of meaning and responsibility. Although it requires guidance, facing and contest, the process remains fundamentally learner-driven. Ethical education, therefore, concerns the development of judgement rather than behavioural obedience.

Virtue ethics complements this educational vision, by modifying emphasis from externally imposed rules to character formation. Comparative and cross-cultural studies indicate that certain core virtues (wisdom, justice, humanity, courage, temperance and transcendence) occur across moral traditions. Although they are differently expressed and ranked (Dahlsgaard et al. 2005, 207–10). This unification does not neutralise plurality. Rather, it offers a shared ethical vocabulary. Therefore, capable of experiencing shared educational judgement, and creating a safe learning environment.

As Koehn observes, virtues guide ethical judgement in concrete situations. This instead of prescribing rules disconnected from contexts (Koehn 2020, 210–7). Within decolonising education, this appears crucial. Moncrieffe emphasises that ethical orientation must emerge dialogically, not be imposed as a hidden universal (Moncrieffe 2022, 13–8). In this sense, virtue ethics aligns with *Bildung* as instinctive educational self-development. It provides resources for ethical orientation in plural educational contexts.

Meaning-oriented reflection, within education, deepens this perspective by emphasising inwardness, motivation and ethical awareness. Educational research suggests that ethical internalisation, i.e. 'transfer learning' occurs when learners engage existentially with content and situations. That, in contrast to than just processing information cognitively (Hattie and Donoghue 2016, 102–6). Self-reflection, therefore, becomes not only a cognitive act, but a formative educational practice shaping ethical consciousness.

The 'Pluriversal Ethical Reflection Framework' as Conceptual Architecture

Against this philosophical background, the PERF is positioned as a reflective architecture for ethical formation in education. The framework integrates macro-, meso- and micro-levels of interpretation. These are connected through a pluriverse horizon and stabilised by virtue ethics. It is conceptual rather than methodological. The framework aims to support self-reflective judgement rather than procedural application.

Macro-Level: Educational Normativity, Meaning and Dooyeweerd

At the macro-level, the PERF draws on Herman Dooyeweerd's philosophy of fifteen modal aspects to convey normativity as structurally embedded. Dooyeweerd separates complex

modalities, e.g. juridical, ethical, pistic, etc., characterised by their own normative logic and meaning (Dooyeweerd 1953–1958, I: 3–35).

Recent interpretations by Verkerk, Glas and Sierksma–Agteres emphasise that Dooyeweerd’s philosophy is not abstract system-building but ethically and existentially oriented. They highlight how modal normativity points beyond instrumental rationality toward orientation, responsibility and trust (Verkerk et al. 2025, 41–58). Meaning, in this account, is not constructed at random but revealed within the consistency of actual reality.

Within education, Dooyeweerd’s modal framework invites reflection on how ethical questions meet with justice, social structures, economic stewardship and worldview commitments. Importantly, it challenges reduction of ethics to a single explanatory register, like efficiency, cultural preference or individual autonomy.

Interpreted pluriversally, Dooyeweerd’s philosophy does not prescribe uniform ethical outcomes. It allows for numerous normative expressions, based on shared dimensions of meaning (Woldring 2014, 233–40). Normativity remains. Yet its expression is addressed within its context.

Meso-Level: Political, Economic, Social-cultural, Technological, Environmental and Legal Factors Analysis and Contextual Normativity

At the meso-level, the PERF employs Political, Economic, Social-cultural, Technological, Environmental and Legal factors analysis (PESTEL) as a framework for interpreting contextual forces shaping environments. Contrasting strategic management applications, PESTEL within the PERF functions as a normatively questioned context-approach-*in-casu*-layer.

Political governance structures define priorities and accountability mechanisms. Economic pressures shape institutional incentives. Social-cultural dynamics influence inclusion and exclusion. Technological infrastructures alter relational patterns. Environmental concerns introduce intergenerational responsibility. While legal frameworks restrict ethical agency. Each dimension carries implicit normative assumptions.

Moncrieffe demonstrates how educational institutions reproduce epistemic hierarchies through policy, assessment and curricular design. Doing this, even when inclusivity is verbally involved (Moncrieffe 2022, 19–24). PESTEL, therefore, becomes a critical interpretive tool. It highlights how frameworks determine which forms of knowledge are established and which are downgraded.

By situating PESTEL within a pluriverse horizon, the PERF reframes contextual analysis from adaptive compliance to ethical interpretation. Context does not dictate ethical judgement but conditions it. This approach aligns with decolonial critiques emphasising the ethical conspicuousness of power, governance and historical location (Maldonado–Torres 2007, 248–52).

Micro-Level: Moral Formation and Education through Meaning-Oriented Reflection

At the micro-level, moral formation is conceptualised through Meaning-Oriented Reflection (MORE3.1.2), as developed by Meeuwsen (2024, 39–45; 2025, 41–4). MORE3.1.2 articulates ethical reflection as a dynamic, integrative and revolving process involving inspiration, intuition, logic, awareness, willing and acting.

These dimensions are not sequential steps but mutually informing aspects of self-reflective judgement. Inspiration refers to an initial, pre-analytical openness to meaning, grounded in inspiration and spiritual receptivity, which functions as the first movement of ethical self-reflection. Intuition alerts to ethical feeling, based on experience and knowledge. Logic structures reasoning. Awareness enables self-reflection on the previous three. Then, ‘willing’ expresses ethical commitment. While ‘acting’ translates self-reflection into responsible practice (Meeuwsen 2024, 39–45; Meeuwsen 2025, 41–4).

This reflective cycle echoes Comenius’ integration of *ratio*, *emotio* and *inspiratio* (Comenius 1657/2019, I–II) and aligns with *Bildung*-oriented pedagogy. Situated within the PERF, MORE3.1.2 integrates macro-level normativity and meso-level context into ethical judgement. The six core virtues, i.e. wisdom, courage, humanity, justice, temperance and transcendence, provide ethical orientation without moral standardisation (Dahlsgaard et al. 2005, 207–13). Transcendence acknowledges that ethical formation often engages ultimate questions exceeding instrumental rationality.

Two Compact Educational Cases

Case 1: AI-based assessment in higher education

To illustrate the integrative functioning of the PERF, consider a case drawn from higher education practice.

A multidisciplinary cohort of students analyses the decision of a European university to partner with a technology firm developing AI-based proctoring software for online examinations. The partnership promises efficiency and fraud prevention but raises concerns about surveillance, data ownership, bias and cybersecurity.

At the macro-level, students analyse the situation through Dooyeweerd’s fifteen modal aspects, identifying juridical concerns (privacy), ethical dimensions (care, responsibility) and pistic aspects (trust in technology) (Dooyeweerd 1953–1958, I: 3–35).

At the meso-level, PESTEL analysis reveals political pressure for performance metrics, economic incentives, technological acceleration and legal ambiguity regarding data protection. Students recognise how institutional context shapes ethical horizons.

At the micro-level, MORE3.1.2 guides reflective engagement. Inspiration opens awareness of moral unease; intuition highlights fairness concerns; logic structures arguments; awareness situates assumptions; willing expresses commitment to academic integrity; acting leads to proposing alternative assessment forms.

This case demonstrates how the PERF supports ethical judgement without prescribing outcomes, while remaining sensitive to pluriverse perspectives and normative responsibilities.

From the perspective of philosophy of education, this case illustrates how ethical judgement in educational settings can be cultivated without reducing education to procedural compliance.

Case 2: Leadership ethics in an intercultural teacher-education programme

A postgraduate teacher-education programme attracts participants from Europe, Africa and Asia/Pacific. A module on “educational leadership” emphasises autonomy, boldness and decision-making pace. Several students express discomfort. They note that leadership in their contexts focuses on relational responsibility and collective sensitivity.

Using the PERF, students analyse the tension:

- Macro-level (fifteen modal aspects): conflicting pistic and ethical orientations regarding authority and responsibility.
- Meso-level (PESTEL): institutional expectations shaped by Western frameworks.
- Micro-level (MORe3.1.2): reflection leads students to recognise biases, articulate commitments and co-design alternative leadership narratives.

The case demonstrates how the PERF supports ethical learning in education without prescribing a singular leadership ideal. From a philosophy of education perspective, it shows how ethical judgement can emerge through meaning-oriented, reflective engagement within educational settings. In this way, education is affirmed as a formative practice of judgement and responsibility, rather than reduced to procedural compliance or instrumental control.

Conclusion on Theological, Philosophical and Educational Significance

Theologically, the framework connects with worldviews that understand education as the formation of the whole person oriented toward responsibility, justice and hope. Drawing on the pistic dimension of meaning highlighted by Dooyeweerd and elaborated by Verkerk et al. (2025, 101–18), moral orientation ultimately involves trust and commitment rather than procedural certainty.

Philosophically, the framework offers an approach to moral formation in plural educational settings. By integrating pluriversality, structured normativity and self-reflective activity, it avoids the dualistic opposition between universalism and relativism.

Educationally, the framework challenges competence-based paradigms by re-focusing on meaning and judgement and ethical imagination as key to education itself.

Further Research

The conceptual nature of the ‘Pluriversal Ethical Reflection Framework’ invites further philosophical, theological and educational inquiry rather than immediate empirical validation. Comparative research may explore relations with critical pedagogy, intercultural ethics and *Bildung*. Narrative and hermeneutic studies could examine meaning-oriented ethical self-reflection in pluriverse contexts.

Meeuwssen’s (2022, 171–91) narrative reflective analogy dialogue, parallel to educational storytelling, represents a possibility for educational design research.

Reflective analogy (Meeuwsen in Moncrieffe 2022, 191)

“Once in a while, Charming School’s professional learning community takes a climate-friendly green train, for their pluriverse field trip to the blue ocean. Next to meaningful learning from each other, addressing the now more conscious needs, enjoying a ‘gezellige’¹ company and having fun together, stimulates their educational thrill. Global social justice without global cognitive justice. All together now, leading towards ‘Something good’.

The weather is nice, the environment is more than cool, and the sun? Never sets.”

Final reflective question for consideration

How can education cultivate ethical judgement and ethical responsibility within epistemically plural contexts while remaining virtuously grounded?

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¹ “Gezellig: Dutch for cosy, enjoyable, intimate, pleasant, welcoming, etc.” (Meeuwsen 2022, 191)

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